

FIND YOUR EFFECTIVE VALORISATION STRATEGY WITH THE IP4OS TOOLBOX.

“As open as possible, as closed as necessary”: a FAIR principle encouraging sharing without unnecessary or inappropriate restrictions.

Copyright: The exclusive legal right to reproduce, publish, and distribute a creative work. Librarians advise on managing and retaining these rights.

Embargo: A temporary restriction delaying open access to outputs.

FAIR Principles: FAIR stands for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable — making research outputs machine-readable to foster sharing, redistribution, and reuse.

FAIR-R²L: FAIR–expansion to FAIR plus ‘Responsibly Licensed’, adding the requirement to datasets being responsibly licensed and legally ready for reuse (whether in research or machine learning workflows or in use by AI).

Freedom to Operate (FTO): The analysis of whether a product or dataset can be used, shared, or commercialised without infringing third-party rights.

Intellectual assets: “[...] any result or product generated by any R&I activities” during (research artefacts) and at the end (research results) of a research process, such as Intellectual Property Right, data, know-how, and more. Not all assets are (potentially) eligible for Intellectual Property protection.

Examples of Intellectual Assets:

1) Publications (papers, reports etc.); 2) Lectures, talks, presentations, learning material; 3) Inventions (and utility models); 4) Data sets (raw/processed data); 5) (Industrial) Designs; 6) Software and Code; 7) Multimedia; 8) Protocols and (research) methods; 9) Technical reports; 10) Topographies of integrated circuits; 11) Geographical information; 12) others

Intellectual Property “means the result of intellectual activities that is eligible for legal protection (by Intellectual Property rights) and includes inventions, literary and artistic works, symbols, names, images, and designs.” IP4OS focuses on finding ways of managing Intellectual Property Rights that are compatible with Open Science and Knowledge Valorisation goals, including potential downstream commercialisation.

Knowledge Valorisation: the “[...] process of creating social, [environmental] and economic value from knowledge by linking different areas and sectors and transforming data, know-how and research results into sustainable products, services, solutions and knowledge-based policies that benefit society” ([source](#)).

This transformation is determined by availability, re-utilisation and re-usability of intellectual assets. The application of Intellectual Property Rights and Open Science practices serves as a key instrument for research Knowledge Valorisation, defining the control and/or specification of utilisation of intellectual assets and safeguarding the author’s/innovator’s rights.

The **simple Knowledge Valorisation Rubric** is an effective tool to assess a) focus of intellectual assets (producing new or re-using existing intellectual assets), b) the level or conditions of re-use, c) timing for/of reuse.

Licensing: The process of granting permission for others to use intellectual property under defined conditions, for example, software licences.

“**Open [...]**” does not mean ignoring Intellectual Property Rights or allowing free commercial use. It means increasing FAIR access to research outputs to boost innovation capacity.

“**Open Access**” refers in particular to the release of research outputs such as articles or books in a way that they are accessible and reusable without a fee. There are different business models associated with open, in terms of who pays for publication costs and how.

Open licensing: an approach to licensing that aims to maximise possibilities for access and re-use. The most famous examples of these are Creative Commons licences.

Open Science is “an approach to research based on open cooperative work that emphasises the sharing of knowledge, results and tools as early and widely as possible” ([source](#)). It aims at (long-term) availability of intellectual assets for further knowledge circulation and gain, reusability, co-creation and enhancement of innovative power and dissemination through no-or-low barrier (according to “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”) access to scientific outputs, enabling reuse for discovery, validation, and cumulative knowledge building. Openness fosters quality assurance and replicability, and strengthens reliability, integrity, and trust in science.

Examples of Open Science practices:

1) Applying the **FAIR** principles to research outcomes; 2) **pre-registration** and **registered report**; 3) publishing in **Open Access** journals; 4) Depositing and sharing data, software, scripts, and algorithms in **open repositories**; 5) Using **open licences** (e.g. Creative Commons, Open Hardware Licence etc.); 6) Providing **data management plans** (DMPs); 7) Using **open data**; 8) **Documenting code** to support reuse and reproducibility; 9) **Sharing experimental protocols, workflows, and methodologies**; 10) Posting **preprints** to share results prior to formal publication; 11) others

Regulatory Exclusivity: A non-patent intellectual property tool granting temporary market protection based on regulatory data, relevant in pharmaceutical valorisation strategies.

Repository: A digital platform – typically non-commercial – used to store, manage, and provide access to research outputs.

Rights Retention: The practice of ensuring authors keep their rights, only offering specific possibilities to publishers when signing publishing agreements.

Secondary Publication Rights (SPR): A legal framework allowing authors to make a version of their published articles openly accessible through institutional or non-profit repositories, typically upon or after journal publication, and potentially under certain conditions.

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KNOWLEDGE VALORISATION PATHWAY IN A CONCERTED IP-OS APPROACH

Knowledge Valorisation does not happen automatically. It results from deliberate decisions on role focus, openness, and timing (see Knowledge Valorisation Rubric), supported by Intellectual Property and Open Science tools.

Take your idea, define its purpose and intended outcomes collaboratively, and consider how it will **create value beyond research**—by **economic growth, societal benefit, environmental impact, improved policy-making, or others?**

As your research unfolds, look beyond the **final result** to the **intellectual assets it generates along the way**. These artefacts deserve to be shared, protected, and reused—through **Intellectual Property Rights and Open Science practices**—so they create value rather than fade into obscurity. Guiding question: *How should access, re-use, and Intellectual Property arrangements be designed to maximise research impact?*

IDEA GARDEN

DEFINING THE INTENDED RESEARCH IMPACT AND VALORISATION PATHWAYS

RESEARCH LIFECYCLE

Use the [simple Knowledge Valorisation Rubric](#) to support decisions.

VALUES & IMPACT FOR ECONOMY, SOCIETY, ENVIRONMENT

- Societal benefit
- Economic growth
- Environmental impact

- Improved policymaking
- (New/Follow-up) Collaboration and others

- Publication
- Data set
- Innovation / Technology

- Code
- Methodology and others

- Copyright
- Patent
- Secondary Publication Rights

- (Open) License
- (Open) Access and others

Open license applicable to data, code, protocols, etc.

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The micro-level library contains material suitable for this curriculum and the practice of multi-professional teams. It was developed using a FAIR-by-Design methodology, which involved collecting a consortium-wide call for contributions and, where appropriate, cross-linking relevant materials from the [GATE initiative](#).

The following resources are recommended as additional reading in the fields of Intellectual Property and Open Science, classified according to the target groups:

Group A - IP experts and intermediaries:

- Knowledge and Technology Transfer Professionals
- Infrastructure providing stakeholders in the EU R&I system (e.g. RFOs, RPOs, Publishers, Companies working on science communication & dissemination in EU projects)
- Entrepreneurship Officers
- Research Librarians
- Data Managers / Data Stewards
- Research Managers
- Policymakers (as promoters and supporters of scientific messages and tools)

Group B - Experts performing research (in need of IA management for their work/projects)

- Open Science Ambassadors
- Researchers (at all stages of their career in different fields)
- Research students (BA-, MA-, PhD candidates)
- Academic and University lecturers
- Innovation Managers in Industry & SMEs (collaborating with public sector)
- RPO's professional, managerial, and/or academic staff
- Entrepreneurship Officers
- Open Science Ambassadors
- RPO's professional, managerial, and/or academic staff
- Innovation Managers in Industry & SMEs
- Innovators from Spin-Offs and Start-Ups
- Researchers (at all stages of their career in different fields)

Group C - Trainers in IP or research

- Knowledge and Technology Transfer Professionals
- Open Science Ambassadors
- Teaching Librarians
- RPO's professional, managerial, and/or academic staff
- Entrepreneurship Officers
- Academic and University lecturers

Open Science Guide: Development of RPO's Open Science Strategy — DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15124402; *Use:* Guide for RPOs to establish an Open Science ecosystem aligned with the EC; **Audience: A.**

Open Science Guide: RDM & FAIR Training Framework for RPOs — DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15124383; *Use:* Guide for RPOs on Open Science and FAIR infrastructures, services, practices, training; **Audience: A.**

An introduction to the topic of Open Science for researchers in business studies and economics — DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15348619>. *Use:* Introduction to Open Science, Open Data and FAIR-principles; **Audience: B.**

Open Economics Guide — Available at: <https://openeconomics.zbw.eu/ueber-den-open-economics-guide/>. *Use:* Good scientific practice with Open Science; **Audience: B.**

Repository of Best Practices | Research and Innovation — Available at: <https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/research-area/industrial-research-and-innovation/eu-valorisation-policy/knowledge-valorisation-platform/repository>. *Use:* Overview of European valorisation practices; **Audience: B.**

The societal impact of Open Science – a scoping review — DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10559446. *Use:* European study on the academic, economic, and societal impacts of Open Science; **Audience: B.**

Creative Commons license chooser — Available at: <https://creativecommons.org/chooser/>. *Use:* Selecting a suitable licence for publication; **Audience: B.**

Copyright Information Point by TU Delft — Available at: <https://www.tudelft.nl/library/support/copyright>. *Use:* Copyright tool specifying and explaining usage options after specific scenario selection; **Audience: B.**

License Clearance Tool — Available at: <https://lct.ni4os.eu/lct/login>. *Use:* Selecting licence and finding clearance based on an existing resource and clearance of compatibility with resources based on a target licence; **Audience: B. Audience: B**

Public License selector — Available at: <https://ufal.github.io/public-license-selector/>. *Use:* Selection of a suitable licence for the publication of software and data; **Audience: B.**

Open policy finder — Available at: <https://openpolicyfinder.jisc.ac.uk/>. Use: Check the level of openness supported by individual journal, publisher or funder; **Audience: B**

Journal Checker Tool — Available at: <https://journalcheckertool.org/>. Use: Check which publishing options are supported by your funder's OA policy; **Audience: A/B/C**

Copyright the Card Game — Available at: <https://copyrightliteracy.org/resources/copyright-the-card-game/>. Use: Game on understanding copyright; **Audience: B**

The Publishing Trap — Available at: <https://copyrightliteracy.org/resources/the-publishing-trap/the-publishing-trap-online/>. Use: Game on exploring the impact of scholarly communications choices and discussing the role of open access in research; **Audience: B**

Helmholtz Open Science Policy — DOI: doi.org/10.48440/os.helmholtz.056; Use: Helmholtz's policy strategy on Open Science; **Audience: A/B.**

Licensing FAIR Data for Reuse — DOI: [10.1162/dint_a_00042](https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_a_00042). Use: Choosing licences for FAIR data; **Audience: A/B.**

Code of practice on the management of intellectual assets for Knowledge valorisation — ELI: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reco/2023/499/oj>. Use: Practical policy guidance on IA/IP; **Audience: A/B.**

Licensing FAIR Data for Reuse — DOI: [10.1162/dint_a_00042](https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_a_00042). Use: Choosing licences for FAIR data; **Audience: A/B.**

Legal Interoperability of Research Data: Principles and Implementation Guidelines (RDA-CODATA) — DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.162241](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.162241). Use: Licensing/reuse principles; **Audience: A/B/C.**

Open Science and intellectual property rights — How can they better interact? State of the art and reflections (Executive Summary) — DOI: [10.2777/347305](https://doi.org/10.2777/347305). Use: Macro framing of IP-OS interplay; **Audience: A/B/C.**

The “A” of FAIR – As Open as Possible, as Closed as Necessary (Landi et al., Data Intelligence) — DOI: [10.1162/dint_a_00027](https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_a_00027). Use: Conceptual anchor for openness decisions; **Audience: A/B/C.**

Legal Interoperability of Research Data: Principles and Implementation Guidelines (RDA-CODATA) — DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.162241. *Use:* Licensing/reuse principles; **Audience: A/B/C.**

An intellectual property action plan to support the EU's recovery and resilience — CELEX: 52020DC0760; *Use:* EU's Intellectual Property Action Plan to strong IP protection fostering competitiveness and EU economy; **Audience: A/B/C**

Guiding Principles for Knowledge Valorisation — ELI: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reco/2022/2415/oj>; *Use:* European Commission's general overview on Knowledge Valorisation; **Audience: A/B/C**

ERA Policy Agenda 2025-2027 — ELI: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/C/2025/3593/oj/eng>; *Use:* Overview of EU's research agenda; **Audience: A/B/C**

The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity — DOI: 10.26356/ECOC ISBN 978-3-9823562-3-5; *Use:* Guidance on Research Integrity; **Audience: A/B/C**

European IP Helpdesk Bulletin / June 2019: IP Licensing — ISSN:2599-9427. Catalogue number: EA-AG-19-001-EN-N. *Use:* Guidance on Intellectual Property and Technology Transfer; **Audience: A/B/C.**

European IP Helpdesk Bulletin / December 2019: Go-To-Market — ISSN: 2599-9427. Catalogue number: EA-AG-19-002-EN-N. *Use:* Strategic exploitation of Intellectual Property; **Audience: A/B/C.**

European IP Helpdesk Bulletin / December 2023, Societal Value Creation — ISSN: 2599-9427. EA-AG-23-003-EN-N. *Use:* Access to innovations and technology in times of crises; **Audience: A/B/C.**

European IP Helpdesk Bulletin / December 2023, Open Science — ISSN: 2599-9427. EA-AG-23-002-EN-N. *Use:* Making research results and data accessible to stakeholders; **Audience: A/B/C.**

European IP Helpdesk Bulletin / June 2025, Insights: Code of Practice on Industry-Academia Co-creation for Knowledge Valorisation — ISSN: 2599-9427. Catalogue number: EA-01-24-060-EN-N. *Use:* Understanding the Code of Practice; **Audience: A/B/C.**

Guide to Legal Aspects in Research Data Management (FAIRmat) — DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11083303. Use: Legal/RDM quick reference; **Audience: A/B/C.**

How FAIR-R Is Your Data? Enhancing Legal and Technical Readiness for Open and AI-Enabled Reuse — DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17696933. Use: Expansion of FAIR to FAIR and Responsibly Licensed (ethical and legal aspects). Checklist on metadata annotation for AI and machine workflows; **Audience: A/B/C.**

Toward the FAIR-R principles: Advancing AI-Ready Data — DOI: 10.2139/ssrn.5164337. Use: Expansion of FAIR principles to AI readiness for better metadata annotation; **Audience: A/B/C.**

Rechtsfragen bei Open Science — DOI: 10.15460/HuP.211. Use: Overview of legal issues relating to Open Science; **Audience: A/B/C.**

Lernzielmatrix zum Themenbereich Forschungsdatenmanagement (FDM) — DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15025246. Use: Teaching research data management; **Audience: B/C.**

Horizon Europe — Open Science (guide/brochure) — DOI: 10.2777/18252. Use: Funders' OS expectations; **Audience: B/C.**

Toolkit for Researchers on Legal Issues in Research Data Management (OpenAIRE) — DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2574619. Use: Step-by-step legal/RDM guidance; **Audience: B/C.**

Code of practice on industry-academia co-creation for Knowledge Valorisation — ELL: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reco/2024/774/oj>; Use: Guidance to foster collaboration between industry and academia; **Audience: A/C**

Progress on Open Science: Towards a Shared Research Knowledge System (OSPP Final Report) — DOI: 10.2777/00139. Use: Policy context for OS; **Audience: A/C.**

Improving access to and reuse of research results (Executive Summary) — DOI: 10.2777/780253. Use: Policy measures for access/reuse; **Audience: A/C.**

The Open Science Training Handbook (FOSTER/TIB) — DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1212496. Use: Ready-to-use training activities; **Audience: C.**

Ten quick tips for navigating intellectual property in FAIR educational resources — DOI: doi.org/10.48440/os.helmholtz.056; Use: *Developing intellectual property compliant and FAIR OER*; **Audience: C.**